

ASTRAL

All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture

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1 Summary

This report describes the requirements IMTA systems must comply with in order to meet current standards and contains recommendations on how to develop, in the longer term, new IMTA eco-value chains delivering organic standards. The key findings of this analysis of the aquaculture eco-certification landscape is that the current certification schemes are designed for monoculture of aquaculture species. Certification for some species such as seaweed are becoming more widely available. Certification schemes for IMTA, as yet, have not been developed, such certification however would recognise IMTA and the benefits it would bring to enhance consumer trust and improve social license to operate. As the aquaculture industry moves to become a more organically focused industry, IMTA should strive to function as organic production systems. Global marketing and labelling of certified products should recognise IMTA produce thus allowing for customers to make informed purchases.

Legislation should be reviewed to allow for IMTA products to be fully marketable. Legislative and administrative processes should be improved to allow for the advancement of IMTA production. Policy at national levels should include the development of IMTA and promote the diversification of monoculture to IMTA production. Commercialisation of IMTA systems and products needs to be developed by enhancing policy and acknowledging the ecosystem services that can be provided by IMTA production.

While all the ASTRAL IMTA labs meet the regulatory and licensing requirements for aquaculture production, the open water IMTA non-commercial production site at Lehanagh Pool in Ireland currently is not certified under any of the listed schemes for its species but does operate to organic standards; all farmed abalone products produced at IMTA lab South Africa are listed as green 'sustainable seafood' by the WWF South African Sustainable Seafood Initiative (SASSI); the open water IMTA production site in Scotland is a non-commercial experimental site where the cultivated seaweed is licenced for all markets; however, organic certification remains to be implemented; IMTA lab Brazil is the only ASTRAL IMTA system that is currently being assessed for certification, a methodology is being developed.

2 Introduction

2.1 ASTRAL

ASTRAL is developing new, sustainable, profitable and resilient value chains for integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) production within the framework of existing, emerging and potential Atlantic markets. The project gathers four IMTA labs including open offshore (Ireland, Scotland), partial recirculation inshore (South Africa) and recirculation inshore (Brazil) systems and one prospective IMTA lab (Argentina), focusing on a regional challenge-based perspective, including fish, mollusc, echinoderm, crustacean and algae species.

Analysis of the current regulatory requirements for aquaculture production has been analysed along with the policy approaches in each of the ASTRAL jurisdictions. This report compiles recommendations for regulation and certification of IMTA.

2.2 IMTA

The EUMOFA (European Market Observatory for Fisheries and Aquaculture products)¹ defines Integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) as follows:

“The practice which combines, in the appropriate proportions, the cultivation of fed aquaculture species (e.g. finfish/shrimp) with organic extractive aquaculture species (e.g. shellfish/herbivorous fish) and inorganic extractive aquaculture species (e.g., seaweed) to create balanced systems for environmental sustainability (biomitigation), economic stability (product diversification and risk reduction) and social acceptability (better management practices)”.

Barrington *et al.* (2009)² in a FAO technical paper stated that ‘most of the countries with coastlines in temperate regions of the globe have some level of aquaculture ongoing, although very few have ongoing IMTA systems near or at commercial scale. IMTA has enormous potential for growth’. This technical paper advises the following:

‘In order to ensure the expansion of IMTA several steps should be taken where appropriate.

These include:

1) Establishing the economic and environmental value of IMTA systems and their co-products - seaweeds and invertebrates can be very profitable cultured species, not only for

¹ EUMOFA, Blue Bioeconomy Report 2023.

² Barrington, K., Chopin, T. and Robinson, S. 2009. Integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) in marine and temperate waters. In D. Soto (ed.), Integrated mariculture. A global review. *FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture Technical Paper*. No. 529. Rome, FAO. 2009. 183p

their services as effluent biomitigators, but also as differentiated premium cash crops diversifying the aquaculture sector and reducing risks.

2) Selecting species appropriate to the habitat and available technologies - native species should be used, to avoid problems with invasive, and potentially harmful, species.

3) Selecting species according to the environmental and oceanographic conditions of the sites proposed for IMTA development, and also according to their complementary ecosystem functions.

4) Selecting species that are capable of growing to a significant biomass in order to capture many of the excess nutrients and remove them efficiently at harvesting time.

5) Selecting species that have an established or perceived market value and for which the commercialization will not generate insurmountable regulatory hurdles.

6) Promoting effective government legislation/regulations and incentives to facilitate the development of IMTA practices and the commercialization of IMTA products.

7) Educating government/industry/academia and the general public about the benefits of IMTA. This can be done by disseminating knowledge through diverse media supports targeting diverse audiences.

8) Establishing the Research & Development & Commercialisation continuum to ensure success in the long term for IMTA to become a widespread reality.'

The European Commission's Strategic guidelines for a more sustainable and competitive EU aquaculture for the period 2021 to 2030³ states that 'the environmental performance of the EU aquaculture sector can be further improved. This can be achieved by: (i) ensuring that environmental legislation is applied and its objectives are met; (ii) further mitigating the impact of aquaculture; and (iii) promoting aquaculture with lower environmental impact and aquaculture that provides ecosystem services. Promoting the development of organic aquaculture and other aquaculture systems with lower environmental impact, such as: energy-efficient recirculating aquaculture systems, integrated multi-trophic aquaculture systems (IMTA), as well as the diversification to lower-trophic species (molluscs and other invertebrates and algae and herbivore fish), were identified as issues that should be addressed to achieve greater potential for the aquaculture sector.

³ Strategic guidelines for a more sustainable and competitive EU aquaculture for the period 2021 to 2030 (COM/2021/236)

The European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF⁴) programme 2021 – 2027, stipulates that the fund should be used to promote sustainable aquaculture practices such as organic production. The fund helps achieve sustainable fisheries and conserve marine biological resources. This leads to

- food security through the supply of seafood products
- growth of a sustainable blue economy
- healthy, safe and sustainably managed seas and oceans

The Code of Conduct for Responsible Food Business and Marketing Practices is one of the first deliverables of the EU Farm to Fork Strategy⁵ and an integral part of its action plan. It sets out common aspirations and indicative actions ‘between the farm and the fork’, such as food manufacturers, food service operators and retailers, can voluntarily align, commit and contribute to support the transition towards sustainable food systems. This code seeks to provide/promote more sustainably-produced food products/meals (e.g. sustainably-produced organic food; higher animal welfare standards; sustainable fisheries, aquaculture and algae products). It also seeks to promote and support innovation and/or increased use of sustainable agricultural, aquaculture and fisheries practices in partnership with farmers/fishers, in particular aiming at:

- climate change mitigation (e.g. reducing emissions and nutrient losses)
- improving biodiversity
- enhancing circularity and resource-efficiency
- climate adaptation while contributing to improvement of farmers' livelihoods (e.g. crop diversification)
- improving animal welfare and human/animal health (e.g. promoting responsible use of medicines in animals; One Health Aquaculture Approach)
- sustainable management of natural resources (such as land, soils and fish stocks)

⁴ Regulation (EU) 2021/1139 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 7 July 2021 establishing the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund and amending Regulation (EU) 2017/1004

⁵ [Farm to Fork Strategy \(europa.eu\)](https://european-council.europa.eu/media/en/press-communications/infographic/infographic_farm-to-fork-strategy_en.pdf)

2.3 IMTA in Ireland

Monoculture of aquaculture species is well established in the marine environment in Ireland with a 10% increase in production in 2021⁶ to 42,812 t. The main aquaculture species are organic salmon (*Salmo salar*); oyster (*Ostrea edulis* and *Crassostrea gigas*); rope grown mussel and seabed cultured mussels (*Mytilus edulis*). Ireland has one of Europe's most active seaweed industries, however the seaweed harvest is relatively small (approx. 30,000 wet t per annum)⁷, mainly the brown seaweed *Ascophyllum nodosum*. Cultivation of seaweed is still small scale in Ireland but there is a paucity of reliable data in the public domain about the status of the culture of seaweed. The main species currently cultured are largely species of kelp, *Alaria esculenta*, *Saccharina latissima* and *Laminaria digitata*. Research into IMTA continues in Ireland with pilot scale research projects taking place, however no commercial marine IMTA currently exists in Ireland. Ireland's Draft National Strategic Plan for Sustainable Aquaculture⁸ sets out plans to enhance aquaculture circular economy through developing the potential for innovations in IMTA such as new species, products, bay area IMTA and utilisation of waste products. It also promotes opportunities to reduce the carbon footprint of Irish aquaculture through the wider adoption of IMTA. This plan also recognises the ecosystems services that are provided by IMTA production practices.

2.4 IMTA in Brazil

Aquaculture in Brazil is centred on freshwater fish production Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) and Tambaqui (*Colossoma macropomum*), Pacific white leg shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*), oysters (*Crassostrea gigas*) and mussels (*Perna perna*) (Figure 1). According to the last statistical analysis, the freshwater finfish aquaculture was estimated at 800,000 t, marine shrimp production of 95,000 t, production of oyster and mussels of 23,000 t.

Freshwater fish species are the only group cultured in all states, while the production of bivalves (mussels and oysters) is present in all the 17 coastal states, but the main production occurs in Santa Catarina state. Marine shrimp farming is concentrated in the states of the Northeast, where the warm temperature is constant all year.

⁶ BIM Annual Aquaculture Report 2022

⁷ Irish Macro-Algal Cultivation Strategy to 2030.

⁸ <https://www.gov.ie/pdf/?file=https://assets.gov.ie/231811/0c06ecfc-aceb-4db6-bdf7-bc9f4bbb1022.pdf#page=null>

Figure 1. Distribution of the major groups of species farmed in each Brazilian state

Source: Walenti et al., 2021. Aquaculture in Brazil: past, present and future. Aquaculture Reports 19.

Even though aquaculture activity is carried out in conventional systems (monoculture), some initiatives seek to modernize production systems, especially those that allow for increased productivity and reduction of environmental impact.

Super-intensive production of shrimp and fish in biofloc systems is sustainable and biosecure compared to monoculture systems. The biofloc is composed of uneaten feed, faeces, secretions, and their associated algal, bacterial, and micro-plankton communities. The biofloc provides the substrate for microbial nitrification of toxic ammonia to nitrate, in the same production tank, and eliminates the necessity for external treatment and/or water exchange, improving economic and environmental sustainability. Initially the biofloc systems were used in the nursery phase and in recent years some farms are using this system in the grow out phase for tilapia and marine shrimp production.

Multitrophic aquaculture is very recent in Brazil. In the last 3 years, the first initiatives began, with 2 farms implementing integrated production of marine shrimp, molluscs and seaweed, followed by another 2 production sites with integrated production of marine shrimp and tilapia in biofloc systems.

2.5 IMTA in South Africa

The South African aquaculture sector is still in its infancy and production is focused on a few high-value species, such as perlemoen abalone (*Haliotis midae*), Pacific oysters (*Magallana gigas*), mussels (*Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Choromytilus meridionalis*) and finfish, including dusky kob (*Argyrosomus japonicus*) and yellowtail (*Seriola lalandi*) as well as freshwater rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*), tilapias (*Oreochromis mossambicus* and *O. niloticus*) and African sharptooth catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*). A total of 225 aquaculture farms were reported to be operational during the year 2019, with 35 of the farms cultivating marine species and 190 farms cultivating freshwater species. The total annual production of the country's aquaculture industry, excluding seaweed production, in 2019 was 7085.65 t. The marine sector contributed 5112.79 t, while the freshwater sector contributed 1972.86 t. In the marine sector, mussels are the leading sub-sector by volume with 3053.46 t produced in 2019, followed by abalone with 1656.53 and then oysters with 382.70 t. However, the abalone sub-sector is by far the most successful of the aquaculture sub-sectors in terms of value and was comprised of 16 farms in 2019. All current commercial seaweed aquaculture in South Africa is land-based. The green seaweed *Ulva* and the red seaweed *Gracilaria* are grown on commercial land-based, pump-ashore abalone farms. Although the official figures for 2019 gives a production figure of 2154.54 t for these seaweeds, it is estimated that more than 3000 t per annum is currently produced. Most of this is *Ulva* grown in paddle raceways, with some *Gracilaria* grown in aerated tanks.

Several South African commercial aquafarms practice IMTA. At least five large farms grow *Ulva* in abalone effluent water and feed this back to abalone, thus recycling nutrients sourced from feed and excreted by the animals. This production represents more than 90% of the value of South African marine aquaculture. More than 2000 t fresh weight of *Ulva* are also grown per annum on South African abalone farms, which is largely used on-farm as a supplementary feed.

2.6 IMTA in Scotland

Aquaculture is a growing food production industry in Scotland, providing important revenue and employment opportunities especially within rural and coastal communities. Production is centred largely on marine and freshwater finfish and shellfish, predominantly in single-species (monoculture) operations. Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) is Scotland's top food export with over 205k t produced in 2021. Other finfish species include rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*), brown/sea trout (*Salmo trutta*), halibut (*Hippoglossus hippoglossus*) and cleaner fish (e.g. lump sucker *Cyclopterus lumpus*) -

in descending order of production volume and value (Munro, 2022⁹). Scottish shellfish production is dominated by blue mussels (*Mytilus* spp.) with 9.1k t produced in 2021, followed by Pacific oysters (*Crassostrea gigas*), native oysters (*Ostrea edulis*), king and queen scallops (*Pecten maximus* and *Aequipecten opercularis*) and a combined total first sale value of approximately £10.4 million (Munro & Murphy, 2023¹⁰). A seaweed industry is developing in Scotland including operations focussing on a single species or species group as well as those exploring the potential of co-location/cultivation with other species groups, primarily shellfish. The kelp species *Alaria esculenta* and *Saccharina latissima* are considered within the value chain of Scottish IMTA models and have been tested and refined within ASTRAL. Other species of seaweed have been considered, though low productivity (e.g. *Laminaria digitata* and *Ulva* spp.) and/or poor seeding success (e.g. *Palmaria palmata*) necessitates further work to include these species within the value chain of Scottish IMTA models.

Shellfish cultivation is well established in Scotland and benefits from mature cultivation methodologies (e.g. mussels and oysters) and markets (e.g. scallops). Their integration with other forms of aquaculture requires evidence of greater efficiency, quality and/or productivity to drive changes in established cultivation practices.

2.7 IMTA in Argentina

Aquaculture in Argentina is a marginal activity with a historical annual maximum production of 4,028 t registered in 2014. The activity is concentrated in two freshwater fish, the native *pacú* (*Piaractus mesopotamicus*) and the non-native rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*), covering almost 90% of the countries production. Marine aquaculture has been focused on mussels (*Mytilus* spp.) at small artisanal-pilot scale, while no productive marine fish farming has been established despite several attempts. In 2012 the national government lunched the call INNOVACUA¹¹ to finance an IMTA project on a pilot-commercial scale in the Beagle Channel through the program *Argentina Innovadora 2020*¹². This project was designed as a collaborative consortium between academic, scientific, government, and private sectors interested in the feasibility and profitability of an innovative IMTA project. The IMTA was structured to produce 1,000k t/y of rainbow trout in open cages located in the Beagle

⁹ Munro 2022. Scottish Fish Farm Production Survey 2021. Marine Scotland Science.

¹⁰ Munro, L.A., and Murphy, J. 2023. Scottish Shellfish Farm Production Survey 2022. Marine Scotland.

¹¹ http://www.agencia.mincyt.gob.ar/upload/Bases%20y%20Condiciones%20INNOVACUA%202016_final.pdf

¹² <https://www.argentina.gob.ar/ciencia/argentina-innovadora-2030/plan-argentina-innovadora-2020>

Channel, integrated with blue mussels (*Mytilus chilensis*) on long-lines, surrounded by macroalgae (*Macrocystis pyrifera*). However, the project failed to pass the evaluation stage and was not funded.

The only IMTA approach in Argentina is being developed by a company¹³ evaluating on an experimental scale the usefulness of the integrated cultivation of green sea urchins (*Arbacia dufrenoyi*) in RAS integrated with *Ulva*. The commercial goal is nutraceutical products obtained from the sea urchins' gonads.

2.8 Advantages of IMTA

The role of IMTA systems is to promote sustainable production in aquaculture. However, sustainability should be addressed and interpreted under social, economic, and environmental dimension. In terms of environmental aspects, ASTRAL evaluates how the systems perform to reduce the waste generation, the environmental footprint, and increase circularity. The reduction of waste is observed when nutrients and total suspended solids are mitigated in absolute terms, as seen with the reductions in nitrogen and phosphorus from the shrimp and abalone farms in multi-trophic systems. Although open systems have no physical barriers and waste is released to the environment, the potential for bioremediation exists in marine cage farming where extractive species are also developed.

Bioremediation is the principal key attribute of circularity within IMTA system, and efforts in ASTRAL are oriented to quantify the nutrient emissions as part of the circularity assessment. Complementarily, ASTRAL investigates the production parameters that support decision making regarding the efficient use of resources in terms of circular feed ingredients, higher recirculation rates, and good practices for infrastructure waste management. ASTRAL is developing a comprehensive and quantitative analysis of how IMTA is aligned with the circular economy concept. A life cycle perspective of IMTA systems is being evaluated by a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), the potential reduction of environmental impacts of multi-trophic production in terms of biomass harvested is being assessed. The synergies between trophic levels with regards to infrastructure elements use and bioremediation are the key drivers for reducing the environmental footprint of IMTA products. The quantification of these benefits is expected to be delivered in the context of ASTRAL Work Package 4 'Circularity and Zero Waste' - Task 4.3 'Environmental assessment under a life cycle perspective', (this deliverable will be available on the ASTRAL website <https://www.astral-project.eu/>).

¹³ <https://promarineantioxidants.com/>

This report has analysed the standards, policy and regulation landscape including environment and cultivation regulatory standards; extending to ‘beyond compliance’ eco-certification schemes and organic certification and seeks to describe the requirements for IMTA systems to comply with to meet current standards and provides recommendations on how to develop new IMTA eco-value chains delivering organic standards (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Process flow for analysis of current IMTA landscape

2.9 ASTRAL IMTA Labs

ASTRAL IMTA production is carried out in five ASTRAL IMTA labs (Figure 3). The term ‘labs’ refers to the locations of the IMTA species production and is not to be confused with a typical laboratory setting. The ASTRAL IMTA labs consist of partial and full recirculation, open-water and land-based production systems.

Figure 3. ASTRAL IMTA Labs

Each ASTRAL IMTA lab has a defined role within the ASTRAL project as follows:

- IMTA lab Ireland will develop and validate cost-effective IMTA processes in **open-water system** (Figure 4). This IMTA lab is operated by the Marine Institute. The MI will explore the feasibility of combined cultivation of Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*), lumpfish (*Cyclopterus lumpus*), European lobster (*Homarus gammarus*), native oyster (*Ostrea edulis*), scallop spp., seaweeds (*Alaria esculenta*, *Saccharina latissima*) and spiny sea urchins (*Paracentrotus lividus*) as part of the Irish IMTA lab, in Lehanagh Pool, Bertraghboy Bay, in Connemara on the West coast of Ireland. Production technologies for these species will be assessed and optimised in the IMTA system. IMTA lab Ireland will operate in line with organic standards to enhance for potential profitability and to mitigate environmental impact.

Figure 4. IMTA open water system

IMTA lab Ireland has defined the **ASTRAL value chain** for the open water system as follows:

Fed species - Atlantic salmon, *Salmo salar* and lumpfish, *Cyclopterus lumpus*.

These species release waste / nutrients into the surrounding water.

Extractive species – Native oyster, *Ostrea edulis* are filter feeders and are intended to partially remove particulate waste as food, recycling waste streams from cultivated fish.

Extractive species – Seaweeds – kelp, *Saccharina latissima* and *Alaria esculenta* absorb dissolved minerals and carbon - recycling waste streams from the fish and shellfish entering the environment.

Novel species – Spiny sea urchin, *Paracentrotus lividus*, are fed with seaweeds grown in the IMTA process enhancing circularity.

- IMTA lab in Brazil will develop and validate cost-effective IMTA in **recirculation inshore Biofloc systems** (Figure 5). This lab is operated by the Federal University of Rio Grande - FURG (Marine Aquaculture Station Institute of Oceanography). This IMTA lab will develop and enhance the marine shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) culture in a Biofloc (BFT) system. Assessments will be carried out to establish the ideal biomass ratios between the marine

white shrimp, tilapia, halophytes, seaweed and molluscs. This task will study the role of seaweeds (*Ulva fasciata*), mollusc (*Crassostrea gasar*), halophytes (*Salicornia neii*) and fish (*Oreochromis niloticus*) on the control of nutrients and organic material in a Biofloc system. During the production process the ammonia and nitrite are transformed by microorganisms (Biofloc) into nitrate and no water renewal is necessary. Water with Biofloc will be recirculated between the tanks to maintain the biosecurity, increase the biomass production, diversify products and reduce the fish and shrimp feed conversion rate. Additionally, microbial communities from the tanks and the different species included in the IMTA systems will be monitored. Correlations among microbial diversity, species welfare, Biofloc systems productivity, environmental conditions and water quality will be assessed.

Figure 5. IMTA closed system

IMTA lab Brazil has defined the **ASTRAL value chain** for the close system as follows:

Fed species - marine white shrimp, *Litopenaeus vannamei*, These species release nutrients and organic material (Biofloc) into recirculation system.

Extractive species – Native oyster, *Crassostrea gasar*, and tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus*, are filter feeders filtering out Biofloc as food, reusing the organic material in the production system.

Extractive species – Seaweed – sea lettuce, *Ulva fasciata*, and marine asparagus, *Salicornia neii*, absorb dissolved nutrients - reusing the nitrate and phosphate accumulated in the production system.

Novel species – *Crassostrea gasar* are responsible to control the biofloc concentration in the IMTA system.

- The IMTA lab of South Africa will develop and validate cost-effective IMTA in **land-based pump ashore systems**. This IMTA lab is operated by the University of Cape Town (UCT) and the Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (DFFE) and is based at two sites – (1) is ca. 200 km east of Cape Town on Buffeljags abalone farm, a commercial aquafarm operated by Viking Aquaculture and (2) is the DFFE Marine Research Aquarium (MRA). In this lab, the physical and chemical parameters of the Abalone-*Ulva* IMTA systems will be monitored, including the microbial community, to provide critical information on biosecurity, species health and system health. Microbiome data will be used to assess correlations among environmental conditions, microbial diversity, species welfare and Abalone-*Ulva* IMTA system productivity. The growth of *Ulva* in recirculation and flow-through systems in aquaculture facilities will be characterised and fertility control in *Ulva* will be investigated. Development and optimization of culture technology to produce of a new high value species, the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*, in IMTA systems will be carried out. Potential for the use of faecal matter from the sea urchin *Parechinus angulosus* as a feed/probiotic for juvenile abalone will be investigated. The South African IMTA lab will generate information on the bacterial, fungal/oomycete and viral microbiome associated with the water and cultured species in integrated systems with different recirculation rates and under different physiochemical conditions. Information and models on *Ulva*'s bioremediation capacity and the factors necessary for controlling reproduction of the seaweed will be investigated, in order to maintain the vegetative state for commercial production. The potential for the production of additional value-added products from the integrated systems will also be investigated, particularly the use of effluent grown *Ulva* as a supplementary feed or feed additive to enhance growth, health, product quality and sustainability of cultured abalone (*Haliotis midae*) and sea urchin (*Tripneustes gratilla*).

Figure 6. Land-based pump-ashore IMTA system

The production system at IMTA lab South Africa is located at Buffeljags abalone farm. It includes (A) Modular abalone-Ulva IMTA systems, arranged as seven platforms on the farm, with each platform composed of four clusters and each cluster consisting of one Ulva paddle-raceway and several (42) abalone tanks. (B) Schematic of Ulva raceway receiving effluent water from the abalone tanks (AEW_In) and bioremediated water leaving these tanks (AEW_Out). (C) Schematic of the IMTA process at Buffeljags Abalone, where the effluent water leaving the abalone tanks is bioremediated by the Ulva before being mixed with 50% fresh seawater and returned to the abalone raceways.

IMTA lab South Africa has defined the **ASTRAL value chain** for the land-based pump ashore system (Figure 6), as follows:

Fed species – South African abalone (perlemoen), *Haliotis midae*, and the tropical sea urchin, *Tripneustes gratilla*.

These species release waste / nutrients into the surrounding water.

Extractive species – Seaweed, *Ulva lacinulata*.

This species absorbs dissolved minerals and carbon - reusing the waste from the shellfish entering the environment.

Novel species – Tropical sea urchin, *Tripneustes gratilla*, are fed with seaweeds grown in the IMTA process enhancing circularity; and the temperate sea urchin, *Parechinus angulosus*, are fed with seaweeds and their faecal material is used as supplementary feed/probiotic for juvenile abalone, *Haliotis midae*, improving abalone growth/health and enhancing circularity.

- The IMTA lab in Scotland, operated by the Scottish Association for Marine Science (SAMS), will develop and validate cost-effective IMTA in an **open-water system**. IMTA lab Scotland will expand its seaweed farm operations and consolidate its IMTA site by cultivating different kelp species (*Alaria esculenta*, *Saccharina latissima*, and *Laminaria sp.*) and shellfish (native oyster *Ostrea edulis*, and king scallop *Pecten maximus*). Other seaweed species with known market potential but less developed cultivation practice in the UK, such as the red seaweed *Palmaria palmata*, and the green seaweed *Ulva sp.*, will be assessed for their deployment and grow-out performance for open-water cultivation. Edible sea urchins, *Echinus esculentus*, will be deployed to control biofouling build-up on shellfish cultivation infrastructure, whilst naturally occurring cleaner fish (*Cyclopterus lumpus*, i.e. lumpsucker) will be quantified. Optimal deployment conditions for seaweeds (e.g. cultivation depth, line orientation, stocking density) will be quantified, and synergies of co-cultivation with other species groups explored. IMTA lab Scotland will collaborate with local seaweed and shellfish producers as well as IMTA lab Ireland to compare cultivation insights. IMTA lab Scotland will develop best practice procedures for native species to promote sustainable and productive IMTA businesses including the development of Operational Welfare Indicators (OWIs) for selected species.

Oyster-Seaweed System

A. Top View

B. Side View

Figure 7. Open water seaweed and oyster production system.

IMTA lab Scotland has defined the **ASTRAL value chain** for the open water system (Figure 7) as follows:

[Inorganic] Extractive species – Seaweeds – kelp (*Saccharina latissima* and *Alaria esculenta*) are fast growing and absorb dissolved inorganic nutrients, minerals and carbon - contributing to nutrient recycling and oxygenation of the cultivation environment.

[Organic] Extractive species – Native oyster (*Ostrea edulis*) are effective suspension feeders, filtering dissolved and particulate organic matter from the cultivation environment whilst providing additional nutrients for seaweeds

Novel species - [Organic] Extractive species – King scallops (*Pecten maximus*) as added high-value species with similar ecological characteristics and synergies to Native oysters.

- The Prospective IMTA lab Argentina will explore local species from the Beagle Channel for IMTA production. These investigations are being carried out by CONICET. The prospective IMTA lab Argentina is a replication case building on knowledge from other IMTA labs and following the overarching approach of ASTRAL. The cultivation potential for species local to

the Beagle Channel in Argentina will be assessed, and appropriate sites for IMTA identified within the Beagle Channel. A number of different species will be evaluated in order to determine suitability - fish: Small Puyen, *Galaxias maculatus*; mollusc: Blue Mussel, *Mytilus chilensis*; Echinoderm: Red sea urchin, *Loxechinus albus*, and Green sea urchin, *Arbacia dufresnii*, and halophyte: Salicornia, *Salicornia magellanica*. Data will be acquired on water quality (dissolved oxygen, pH, water temperature, electrical conductivity, and water turbidity) as one of the primary inputs for choosing the species assemblages and to simulate a productive cycle.

A thorough desk-stop study focussing on biological preferences and constraints, aquaculture experiences and local market, determined that the species with the greatest potential for IMTA were: Small Puyen, fish for fed aquaculture; integrated with salicornia in land based-system, and rope grown blue mussel integrated with red sea urchin for biofouling mitigation.

3 Organic Aquaculture

Organic aquaculture is a farming practice that aims to produce food using natural substances and processes. This means that organic farming strives to improve environmental impact as it encourages:

- responsible use of energy and natural resources
- maintenance of biodiversity
- preservation of regional ecological balances
- enhancement of soil fertility
- maintenance of water quality

Organic farming also encourages a high standard of animal welfare and require farmers to meet the specific behavioural needs of the species being produced.

Organic Food Production in the EU¹⁴

Organic production is an overall system of farm management and food production that combines best environmental and climate action practices, a high level of biodiversity, the preservation of natural resources and the application of high animal welfare standards and high production standards in line with the demand of a growing number of consumers for products produced using natural substances and processes. Organic production thus plays a dual societal role, where, on the one hand, it provides for a specific market responding to consumer demand for organic products and, on the other hand, it delivers publicly available goods that contribute to the protection of the environment and animal welfare, as well as to rural development.

Regulation (EU) 2018/848 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2018 on organic production and labelling of organic products and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 834/2007.

New organic legislation is applicable from 1 January 2022, following the postponement of its implementation for a year. The rules reflect the changing nature of this rapidly growing sector. The new regulation is designed to ensure fair competition for farmers whilst preventing fraud and maintaining consumer trust through the following:

*- production rules are simplified through the phasing out of a number of exceptions and opt outs;
the control system is strengthened thanks to tighter precautionary measures and robust checks along the entire supply chain;*

¹⁴ [Regulation \(EU\) 2018/848 – rules on the organic production and labelling of organic products](#)

producers in third countries will have to comply with the same set of rules as those producing in the EU;

- organic rules cover a wider list of products (e.g. salts, cork, beeswax, wool, etc.) and have additional production rules (e.g. deer, rabbits and poultry);*
- certification will be easier for small farmers thanks to a new system of group certification;*
- there will be a more uniform approach to reducing the risk of accidental contamination from pesticides.*

Principles

Organic production should: respect natural systems and cycles; maintain and improve the state of the soil, water and air, and plant and animal health, and the balance between them; preserve the elements of natural landscapes; use energy and natural resources responsibly; produce a wide variety of high-quality products to meet consumer demand; ensure the integrity of organic production at all stages of the production, processing and distribution processes of food and animal feed; exclude the use of genetically modified organisms (GMOs) and products produced from or by GMOs, other than veterinary drugs; restrict the use of external inputs; design and manage biological processes using methods based on risk assessment and the use of precautionary and preventive measures; exclude animal cloning; ensure a high level of animal welfare.*

Labelling

Labelling, advertising or commercial documents may use terms such as 'eco' and 'bio' to describe an organic product, its ingredients or raw materials.

The labelling of an organic product must be clearly visible on the packaging and contain a reference to the control body that certifies the product concerned.

Since 1 July 2010, the use of the EU logo on organic food products has been mandatory, together with an indication of the origin of raw materials used in the product. This indication must be shown in the same field of vision as the EU logo.

Organic Food Production in Brazil

The standards for production, processing, packaging, identification and marketing of organic plant and animal products were established in the late 1990s (Ordinance No. 505 and Normative Instruction No. 07 of the Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Food Supply – MAPA).

In 2004, Normative Instruction no. 16 of MAPA, which established procedures regarding the registration of raw materials and products of organic animal and vegetable origin.

Specific rules for organic products from aquaculture were defined in Law no. 10,831, which regulated organic aquaculture in the country and was later improved by Normative Instruction no. 28¹⁵.

Organic Food Production in Scotland (UK)

The Soil Association Standards in the UK encompass EU Regulations (834/2007, 889/2008 and 1235/2008) which relate to organic certification. Currently all organic seaweed certified under this standard are supplied from harvesting natural populations of seaweed. There are currently no businesses producing cultivated seaweed under this standard. The principal reason for this disparity is the use of artificial nitrogen fertilizers used to culture clean seaweed propagules needed for the supply of seeded materials for on-growing at cultivation sites. Despite the small quantities needed within the nursery phase, the core principals of organic production prohibit the use of synthetic fertilizers. Organic certified nutrient media mixes are in development, but it will take time to ascertain their effectiveness in a commercial setting.

Organic Food Production in South Africa

South Africa has a growing organic market with products sold either online or in specialized stores, restaurants, and organic markets, as well as in large supermarket chains¹⁶. There is however no current legislation available to govern the production of organic food products in the country, and draft regulations on the control and sale of organic products remains to be promulgated. Despite the lack of specific legislation that applies exclusively to organic produce, there are laws and policies that apply to the production and sale of organic food products in South Africa, including the Agricultural Product Standards Act²³ (APSA) that provides for the Biodynamic and Organic Certification Authority (BDOCA). This Act was set up to regulate and control the sale of organic products, whereas the Perishable Products Export Control Board (PPECB) regulates the export of organically produced organic products. Moreover, private certification systems for organic products are applicable in the country and consists of network certification and third-party certification in collaboration with foreign and locally based certification organisations. Network certification is a process whereby growers, suppliers, and retailers of locally grown food group together and use organic labels, whereas third-party certification is a formal and documented procedure that is carried out by an independent organisation. Legal standards for organic food products that are based on international standards are therefore required to serve as national benchmarks for food production in the country. The South African Agricultural Product Standards Amendment Bill, which is set to become law after the South

¹⁵<https://www.gov.br/agricultura/pt-br/assuntos/sustentabilidade/organicos/legislacao/portugues/instrucao-normativa-interministerial-no-28-de-08-de-junho-de-2011-producao-de-organismos-aquaticos.pdf>

¹⁶ Lim Tung OJ "Organic Food Certification in South Africa: A Private Sector Mechanism in Need of State Regulation?" *PER / PELJ* 2016(19) - DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.17159/1727-3781/2016/v19n0a584>

African national assembly approved it in February 2023, seeks to amend the Agricultural Product Standards Act, 1990, and improve quality control and promote food safety in South Africa. One of the key impacts of the bill will be that exporters, farmers and sellers benefit from guarantees that may come with claims such as “organic”, “free range”, amongst others, that may be authenticated. The bill will ensure that all agricultural products sold and exported from South Africa meet certain quality and safety standards, and that the regulatory framework for agricultural production, health, and food safety is strengthened.

Organic Food Production in Argentina

Since 1999, National Law N° 25,127¹⁷ has been in force, which establishes a control system and bases for ecological, biological, or organic production, with the application authority being the National Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock, Fisheries and Food, through the National Agrifood Health and Quality Service (SENASA in Spanish). SENASA is the entity in charge of preserving and controlling food products, based on the requirements established in Chapter XXIII of the Argentine Food Code, which determines the quality parameters and sanitary conditions, packaging, and labelling of products from fishing and aquaculture production. Under this law, ecological, biological or organic is understood as *“Any agricultural production system, its corresponding agro-industry, as well as collection, capture and hunting systems, sustainable over time and that through the rational management of natural resources and avoiding the use of chemical synthesis products and others with a real or potential toxic effect on human health, provide healthy products, maintain or increase soil fertility and biological diversity, conserve water resources and present or intensify cycles biological soil to supply nutrients for plant and animal life, providing natural systems, plant crops and livestock with conditions that allow them to express the basic characteristics of their innate behaviour, covering physiological and ecological needs”*.

Article 43 of the National Law N° 27,231/15 Sustainable Development of the Aquaculture Sector stipulates that producers can access funds to cover fifty percent (50%) of the costs of projects to obtain quality, origin or organic production certifications. However, there are currently no specific organic aquaculture certificates in Argentina, so the only possibility would be to obtain a certificate for products derived from organic agriculture, with its respective logo approved by Resolution of the Secretariat of Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries N° 1,291/2012¹⁸.

Recently, in 2022, the Joint Resolution N° 11/2022¹⁹ was emitted which state that: On the labelling of packaged aquaculture products intended for the final consumer, whether they are cold-preserved

¹⁷ <https://www.argentina.gob.ar/normativa/nacional/ley-25127-59885/texto>

¹⁸ <https://www.argentina.gob.ar/senasa/programassanitarios/produccion-organica>

¹⁹ <https://www.argentina.gob.ar/normativa/nacional/resoluci%C3%B3n-11-2022-375894/texto>

(refrigerated or frozen), smoked or salted, it must be stated that the product is farmed. For this purpose, one of the following expressions shall be entered on the labels next to the sales name: "Aquaculture Product" or "Aquaculture Product".

3.1 Market Regulation

In Europe, markets are regulated under Regulation (EU) No 1379/2013 — ‘Common organisation of the markets in fishery and aquaculture products’ and Regulation (EU) No 1308/2013 — ‘Common organisation of the markets in agricultural products’. The common organisation of the markets in fishery and aquaculture products (CMO) is an integral part of the CFP and should contribute to achieving its objectives. Under these provisions markets are protected by providing a safety net to agricultural markets through the use of market intervention tools and exceptional measures. It provides transparency measures to allow agricultural producers to better make their production and investment decisions in view of market developments. It aims at improving productivity and quality at the production level, boosting demand and helping EU agricultural sectors to better adapt to market changes and increase their competitiveness through aid to specific sectors. It lays down minimum quality requirements (marketing standards), rules and conditions to ensure the quality of the production process and of the products. It specifies the rules for the use of optional reserved terms for value-adding product features or production processes for a number of products.

4 Compliance

In general, compliance means to follow regulations, policies, standards or legislation set out by a designated country or region. National legislation and regulatory compliances can differ between countries; here we briefly describe aquaculture compliances for each IMTA lab jurisdiction.

4.1 EU Ireland

Aquaculture licensing and regulation in Ireland is the responsibility of the Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM). Irish law states that if one is to engage in aquaculture, they must apply for an aquaculture license under the Fisheries (Amendment) Act 1997. Similarly, the Foreshore Act 1933 (as amended) states if state-owned foreshore will be involved, a companion foreshore license is necessary. The EU Habitats Directive (Directive 92/43/EEC) and the Birds Directive (Directive 79/409/EEC) are two main pieces of European legislation which impact the planning of any Irish aquaculture. Before permission is given for any site to begin construction or production an environmental impact assessment (EIA) may be required to assess whether the site may significantly affect the surrounding environment and ecosystems or conflict with the two previous directives. Legislation surrounding the health state of animal products, food produced from aquaculture systems (e.g. Directive 2006/88/EC which regulates animal health conditions) are set at European level and are implemented into national law.

Since 2019, the salmon industry in Ireland is exclusively produced to EU Organic Standards (EU Organic Aquaculture (Commission Regulation (EC) No 889/2008 of 5 September 2008 laying down detailed rules for the implementation of Council Regulation (EC) No 834/2007 on organic production and labelling of organic products with regard to organic production, labelling and control).

Under EU legislation new species are sometimes listed as novel²⁰, this provides for a high level of protection for human health and consumers' interest.

4.2 Brazil

The Ministry of Aquaculture and Fisheries is the main authority for the management and development of fisheries and aquaculture in Brazil. Alongside the Federal District, States and Municipal Authorities, Ministry of Aquaculture and Fisheries is responsible for the granting of licences and permits for aquaculture. The Institute of the Environment and Renewable Natural Resources

²⁰ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32015R2283&from=EN>

(IBAMA) is concerned with the environment and deals with conservation of natural resources (including aquatic resources), environmental licences and water quality control²¹.

4.3 South Africa

The Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (DFFE) is the lead South African Government agency that is responsible for the management of the marine aquaculture sector. The primary legislation governing marine aquaculture in South Africa is the Marine Living Resource Act No. 18 of 1998, which is administered by the DFFE. To undertake any commercial marine aquaculture activity in South Africa, an applicant must first obtain a “right to engage in marine aquaculture” from the DFFE, in accordance with section 18 of the Marine Living Resources Act, 1998 (Act No. 18 of 1998) (MLRA). The MLRA provides for the granting of a “right” to engage in marine aquaculture, whereas permission to exercise this “right” is granted by means of an annual permit. A “right to engage in marine aquaculture” is valid for 15 years, whereas marine aquaculture permits are renewable and valid for a period of 12 months. Depending on the nature of the aquaculture set-up (offshore or onshore) and the type of species to be cultured and managed, several licences and permits may be needed (see appendix 3). These may include a lease to the right to sea or land space, water usage and waste management licences and permits to import or transport live animals²².

4.4 UK Scotland

Marine finfish, shellfish and seaweed aquaculture in Scotland are licensable activities requiring a Marine Licence regulated by Marine Scotland – Licencing Operation Team (MS-LOT) on behalf of the Scottish Ministers. Additional entities such as NatureScot, the Scottish Environmental Protection Agency (SEPA), the Maritime and Coastguard Agency, the Northern Lighthouse Board and the Public (managed through public consultation events) are all statutory consultees on Marine Licence applications.

As well as a licence to operate farm equipment, a Seabed Lease to develop or operate in an area within 12 nautical miles of the UK coastline must be secured from the Crown Estate (Crown Estate Scotland). Since 2007, all new finfish and shellfish farms in development require planning permission under the ‘Town and Country Planning Act’, issued by the relevant Planning Authority. In order to operate a fin-/shellfish business, authorisation for an Aquaculture Production Business (APB) and

²¹https://firms.fao.org/fi/website/FIRRetrieveAction.do?dom=legalframework&xml=nalo_brazil.xml#tcNB0076

²²https://www.dffe.gov.za/sites/default/files/legislations/firstedition2013september_legalguidefor_aquaculturesectorinsouthafrica.pdf

Aquatic Animal Holding Site Details must be submitted to and granted by Marine Scotland - Fish Health Inspectorate (MS – FHI).

Finfish farms must comply with SEPA guidelines and apply for a licence under the Controlled Activities Regulations (CAR), which monitor and enforce standards of waste products on the seabed underneath sea cages. Finfish farms are listed in Schedule 2 to the 2017 EIA Regulations meaning that they require an EIA. Whilst shellfish farms are not subject to either an EIA or CAR licence, local authorities will determine the environmental consequences of the proposal prior to granting planning permission.

All aquaculture products entering the human food chain must comply with Food Standards Scotland (FSS) to ensure food safety such as monitoring for toxins, pesticides, and environmental and process contaminants.

4.5 Argentina

At a national level, the institution responsible for the administration of the aquaculture sector is the Aquaculture Directorate part of the Under-Secretary for Fishing and Aquaculture, which in turn is part of the Ministry of Agriculture, Husbandry, Fishing and Food²³. However, the provinces of Argentina are autonomous and can adhere to the national law, regulate the activity separately or a combination of both. In this sense, the national constitution establishes that the original domain of the existing natural resources in their territory corresponds to the provinces.

²³<https://www.argentina.gob.ar/agricultura/agricultura-ganaderia-y-pesca/subsecretaria-de-pesca-y-acuicultura>

5 Beyond Compliance

Beyond Compliance describes additional standards which encourage farming practises that strive to exceed the regulatory requirements for production, where farmers comply in a more sustainable manner and or achieve a higher standard of product for market to achieve a better market value.

Voluntary Sustainability Standards (VSS) are private standards that require products to meet specific economic, social and environmental sustainability metrics²⁴. The requirements can refer to product quality or attributes, but also to production and processing methods, as well as transportation.

5.1 Concepts Of Standards, Certification and Labelling²⁵

Standards: documented agreements containing technical specifications or other precise criteria to be used consistently as rules, guidelines or definitions, to ensure that materials, products, processes and services are fit for their purpose. These can include product standards (specifications and criteria for the characteristics of products) and process standards (criteria for the way products are made). Social and environmental standards in agriculture are essentially process standards.

Certifications: certification is a procedure by which a third party gives written assurance that a product, process or service is in conformity with certain standards. Codes of Conduct: a set of rules outlining the responsibilities of, or proper practices for, a supplier. These are normally set by lead companies and allow generation of preferred supplier lists, which lower the cost of doing business for lead companies.

Labels: a certification label is a label or symbol indicating that compliance with standards has been verified. Use of the label is usually controlled by the standard-setting body. Where certification bodies certify against their own specific standards, the label can be owned by the certification body.

²⁴ Krauss, J. E., & Krishnan, A. (2022). Global decisions vs. local realities: Sustainability standards, priorities and upgrading dynamics in agricultural global production networks. *Global Networks*, 22, 65– 88. <https://doi.org/10.1111/glob.12325>

²⁵ <https://www.fao.org/3/y5136e/y5136e07.htm#fn7>

5.2 Beyond Compliance Schemes

Twelve beyond compliance standards/certification schemes have been identified by IMTA Lab partners (Table 1) which potentially apply to the culture of the ASTRAL species in each system. Most of these schemes are structured to certify monoculture of the species involved, IMTA as a production system is not yet recognised for certification in the same manner.

a) Organic - IFOAM

IFOAM – Organics International defines organic agriculture as “a production system that sustains the health of soils, ecosystems and people”. IFOAM is the global umbrella organization for the organic sector. It is a membership-based organisation, in operation in over 100 countries and territories throughout Africa, Asia, Europe, Latin America, North America and Oceania. IFOAM developed a series of tools that help guide policymakers and other organic advocates in developing or improving policies related to organic agriculture. The Organic Regulation Toolkit is aimed at governments and sector organizations looking to develop or improve their national organic standard and regulations.

b) EU Organic Regulation 2018/848

This is European regulation that establishes the principles of organic production and outlines the rules concerning organic production, related certification and the use of indications referring to organic production in labelling and advertising. The regulation sets out specific principles applicable to aquaculture for organic production:

c) The Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC)

ASC promotes environmental sustainability and social responsibility using efficient market mechanisms that create value across the chain in aquaculture. Working with partners across the industry, environmental and scientific community and beyond – all standards and programme updates are developed with help from NGOs, academics, farmers, retailers, and other experts, and are subject to public consultation. The ASC currently has 11 standards covering 17 species groups [abalone; bivalves (clams, mussels, oyster, scallop); flatfish; freshwater trout; pangasius; salmon; seabass, seabream, meagre; seriola and cobia; shrimp; tilapia; tropical marine finfish] and there is also a joint ASC-MSC standard for seaweed.

d) ASC-MSC Seaweed standard

The Seaweed Standard sets a number of requirements for seaweed harvesting and farming practices. The standard applies globally to all locations and scales of seaweed operations, including both harvesting of wild populations and farmed seaweed production to ensure that: Environmentally, seaweed operations must show that they actively minimise their impact on the surrounding natural

environment and socially, seaweed operations must be managed in a responsible manner. Producers must care for their employees, work with the local community and be good and conscientious neighbours.

e) The Marine Stewardship Council (MSC)

The MSC uses an ecolabel and a fishery certification program to contribute to the health of the world's oceans by recognising and rewarding sustainable fishing practices, influencing the choices people make when buying seafood and working with partners to transform the seafood market to a sustainable basis. The MSC Chain of Custody Standard ensures that products are traceable and separated from non-certified products.

f) Global Seafood Alliance (GSA)

The GSA is a worldwide organisation that advances responsible seafood practises through education, advocacy and demonstration. GSA provide trusted assurances through BAP and BSP (Best Seafood Practises) certification. Members include certified producers, corporations and individuals.

g) Best Aquaculture Practises (BAP)

BAP is part of the Global Seafood Alliance which ensures aquaculture is performed in a responsible manner. It does this by a third-party certification program. Certification is verification that producers are following best practise with regard to the environment; social responsibility; food safety and animal health and welfare at each stage of the production chain.

h) Global GAP – Standards for good agricultural practises

Global GAP collaborates with supply chain stakeholders to foster the global adoption of safe, socially and environmentally responsible farming practises by providing industry leading, cost effective and value adding and bench marking solutions. The most widely used Global GAP standard is integrated farm assurance (IFA), which is applicable to aquaculture. This standard allows for the use of the GGN label, a consumer label for certified responsible farming and transparency.

i) EU organic standard for seaweed

Regulation (EC) No 834/2007 lays down a legal framework for organic products. It contains the basic objectives and general principles for organic farming and illustrates the rules on production, labelling, controls and trade with non-European Union (EU) countries. In harmonising the rules on the production, labelling and control of organic products, it seeks to ensure that there is fair competition between producers; and greater confidence in these products among consumers.

Regulation (EC) No 834/2007 was repealed and replaced by Regulation (EU) 2018/848 as of 1 January 2022, it will remain in force until 31 December 2026 to complete the examination of pending applications from non-EU countries.

j) Soil Association Organic Seaweed Standards

The Soil Association standards encompass the EU Regulations but has higher organic standards than required by EU organic regulation in key areas.

k) ISO Standard ISO/TC 234 Fisheries and Aquaculture

The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) is an international standard development organization composed of representatives from the national standards organizations of member countries. An ISO standard is an internationally recognised method for production and processes. It ensures that all participants follow the same set of guidelines, resulting in a safer, more consistent end result. This benefits both the organisation and the customer or end user.

The scope of this standard in the field of fisheries and aquaculture, covers, but is not limited to, terminology, technical specifications for equipment and for their operation, characterization of aquaculture sites and maintenance of appropriate physical, chemical and biological conditions, environmental monitoring, data reporting, traceability and waste disposal.

l) WWF South African Sustainable Seafood Initiative

The WWF SASSI initiative highlights the importance of South Africa's seafood industry and helps to promote it as a sustainable marketplace that influences food security as well as the livelihoods of the local fishing communities. As such, several SASSI tools have been developed that inform consumers of sustainable choices. The SASSI list details what the best choices are by using a traffic light system enabling users to easily identify species under threat. WWF South Africa and SASSI work with a variety of stakeholders including; large fishing companies, marine scientists, government organisations, consumers and retail partners. This collaboration addresses all aspects of the seafood supply chain from sea to fork or farm to fork and effects a positive change to help sustain this industry and protect the environment for the future.

Sustainable Seafood Organisations

The **Global Sustainable Seafood Initiative (GSSI)**²⁶ aligns global efforts and resources to address seafood sustainability challenges. Governed by a Steering Board representing the full seafood value

²⁶ <https://gssiitd.com/>

chain – companies, NGOs, governments and international organizations, including the FAO – GSSI promotes sector-wide collaboration to drive forward more sustainable seafood for everyone.

5.3 Certification of the ASTRAL IMTA labs

IMTA Ireland

The open water production site at Lehanagh Pool in Ireland currently is not certified under any of the listed schemes for any of its species. This production facility is a research site only and does not produce food for consumption by humans. All fed species receive organically produced feed and the salmon smolts that are introduced to the site have come from the Marine Institute hatchery that has certification from the 'Organic: Farm Standard Issue 2.0' - Global Trust Certification. Certification that recognises the IMTA process and products of this type of open water system is not yet available from any of the certification bodies. This IMTA production site meets all the regulatory and licensing standards.

IMTA lab Brazil

The certification process for the FURG IMTA system is underway, in partnership with the certifier AQUACERTI, which is the first company in Brazil focused on aquaculture. AQUACERTI is a startup linked to the State University of São Paulo (UNESP) and has been carrying out the study at FURG since March 2023. AQUACERTI sustainability certification is carried out based on the assessment of environmental, social and economic indicators. These indicators were prepared in accordance with the Sustainable Development Goals established by the United Nations. Data for indicator analysis are obtained throughout the production cycle. Environmental samples are collected on the farm, such as gas emissions, input of nutrients and organic matter into the production system and emission of effluents (nutrients and organic matter) into the environment. Also considered are the amount of water used during production, biomass produced and, when applicable, recycling of nutrients in the system (IMTA). In addition, socioeconomic questionnaires are used to obtain data from the farm and compose the overall assessment. According to the number of indicators that meet the standards of the norm, the farm is classified in a level, which can be bronze, silver or gold, the latter being the one with the best sustainability.

IMTA lab South Africa

The land-based partial recirculation production site at Buffeljags in South Africa is a fully commercial aquafarm run by Viking Aquaculture (<https://www.vikingaquaculture.co.za/abalone/>). The farm is modern, efficient, and environmentally sustainable and is one of the first large commercial abalone farms in South Africa to consistently recirculate ca. 50% of their seawater by making use of the

bioremediation capacity of *Ulva*. The farm produces ca. 350 t abalone and ca. 500 t of *Ulva* annually. All *Ulva* produced at the site is fed back to the abalone as supplementary feed (saving up to 20% in formulated feed costs and contributing to a reduction in fishmeal usage), with none of it sold. Conversely, abalone produced at the site is exported as food to Asian countries, such as Hong Kong, Taiwan, China, Singapore and Malaysia, in the form of live, frozen, canned or dried products. The IMTA production site meets all the regulatory and licensing standards and all farmed abalone products produced at this site are listed as green 'sustainable seafood' by the WWF South African Sustainable Seafood Initiative (SASSI), in contrast to wild harvested abalone, which is listed as non-sustainable (red listed). The production site has a marketing advantage over local competitors because they practice IMTA. The production site is currently not certified under any of the listed schemes but is working towards accreditation with the Aquaculture Stewardship Council based on its existing sustainable practices. There are already one or two abalone aquafarms in South Africa that have managed to obtain certification from the ASC.

IMTA lab Scotland

The open water production site at Port-a-Bhuiltin in Scotland is a non-commercial experimental low-trophic aquaculture site and the produced crops (seaweed and shellfish) do not typically enter the food and feed market. Seaweed cultivation is licenced for all markets; however, organic certification remains to be implemented due the addition of artificial nutrients, primarily nitrate, during the nursery stage (SAMS seaweed nursery) (see section Organic Food Standards UK for further detail).

5.4 IMTA Environmental Services

To a greater or lesser extent, the above-mentioned standards address the environmental aspects that are directly improved when a multi-trophic system is developed, however the certification standards do not assess the produce from IMTA cultivation. Particularly, eutrophication and greenhouse gas emissions (climate change impact) are some of the impacts that are reduced when cultivated extractive species recycle nutrients from fed species and a better use of resources are promoted.

Eutrophication is the excessive nutrient enrichment of an aquatic ecosystem. Input from natural and anthropogenic sources by both agriculture and aquaculture have been recorded to have direct

impacts on the amount and composition of impacts of algae community composition²⁷ and changes in the oxygen concentration²⁸, causing a detrimental knock-on effect to the ecosystem.

As outlined in the compliance section, it is expected as part of the aquaculture application process that Environmental Impact Assessments (EIA) are carried out for many aquaculture species. Part of these assessments are to measure how the presence of aquaculture may impact upon the water quality and sediment within the surrounding environment. Monoculture such as finfish or shellfish can generate considerable amounts of dissolved effluents which can potentially affect the water quality and benthic zones within the vicinity of the fish farm^{29,30}. Benthic impacts are well documented³¹ with the input of organic matter enhancing the microbial processes within sediments, eventually leading to anoxic conditions. To prevent this, functional aquaculture set-ups in most countries must adhere to environmental standards as part of existing regulations.

An IMTA system mimics a natural aquatic ecosystem and is arranged in such a way as to use the nutrient input from aquaculture species, thereby minimising waste production and offering a sustainable approach between fed and extractive species³². Potentially certification schemes with a greater emphasis on water quality control could be more amenable to adapting to the IMTA approach. Several of the beyond compliance certification programmes identified (e.g. ASC, GAP and BAP), set limits on the amount of waste material that can be detected around monoculture before certification can be considered. In such circumstances, IMTA has a greater advantage in that it already contributes to improved water quality. Comparisons between different standards as outlined in the Standards Map³³ show varying levels of criteria with regard to the environment.

²⁷ Streicher, Michael D., Henning Reiss, and Katrin Reiss. "Impact of aquaculture and agriculture nutrient sources on macroalgae in a bioassay study." *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 173 (2021): 113025.

²⁸ Hale, Stephen S., Giancarlo Cicchetti, and Christopher F. Deacutis. "Eutrophication and hypoxia diminish ecosystem functions of benthic communities in a New England estuary." *Frontiers in Marine Science* 3 (2016): 249.

²⁹ Holmer, Marianne, et al. "Monitoring of environmental impacts of marine aquaculture." *Aquaculture in the Ecosystem* (2008): 47-85.

³⁰ Crawford, Christine M., Catriona KA Macleod, and Iona M. Mitchell. "Effects of shellfish farming on the benthic environment." *Aquaculture* 224.1-4 (2003): 117-140.

³¹ Hargrave, B. T., et al. "Assessing benthic impacts of organic enrichment from marine aquaculture." *The Interactions Between Sediments and Water: Proceedings of the 7th International Symposium, Baveno, Italy 22–25 September 1996*. Springer Netherlands, 1997.

³² Nissar, S., Bakhtiyar, Y., Yasir Arafat, M., Ahmad Mir, Z., Ali Khan, N. and Langer, S. (2023) The evolution of integrated multi-trophic aquaculture in context of its design and components paving the way to valorization via optimization and diversification. *Aquaculture*, Vol 565.

³³ Standards Map <https://www.standardsmap.org/en/home>

A food products' carbon footprint is described as the total kg of CO₂ released per kg of finished edible product³⁴. This value encapsulates the entire process of food production from culture, processing, distribution and waste disposal. "Eco-friendly" products are becoming increasingly important to the consumer and reporting the carbon footprint of a product can influence its saleability. Knowing a products carbon footprint can also affect its sustainability, the relative impact on those reliant on the industry and their environment. Long-term sustainability of the industry, and those who rely on it, is affected by the environment and initiatives to quantifying and lower the carbon footprint of products is in the interest of producers.

Greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions from aquaculture were estimated to be 9.30×10^{10} g eq CO₂ in 2009 and will increase to 3.83×10^{11} g eq CO₂ by 2030, which will account for 5.72 percent of anthropogenic N₂O emissions³⁵. Amongst GHGs, methane and nitrous oxide can potentially cause a greater degree of warming per unit realised and are comparatively difficult to sequester after release compared to carbon dioxide³⁶. The term Blue Carbon (BC) refers to organic carbon that can be sequestered and stored by the ocean's coastal ecosystems, in particular seagrass meadows, kelp forests, tidal marshes and mangrove forests. BC potential in mitigating against climate change while also achieving other benefits has received a lot of attention in recent years³⁷. However, the loss of one third of these habitats in recent decades due to anthropogenic influences has had a devastating impact on coastal ecosystems³⁸. Sustainable management of these regions will be essential. This is where the 'Greening' of aquaculture or more specifically the concept of IMTA will play an important role³⁹, by improving fish production and at the same time reducing the impact on the environment. Beyond compliance certification programmes can also take into consideration how much GHG emissions an aquaculture system is producing but by using the IMTA method the amount of carbon

³⁴ Lutz 2021, Assessing the carbon footprint of aquaculture. The Lutz Report, Fish Site Media: [Assessing the carbon footprint of aquaculture | The Fish Site](#)

³⁵ Hu, Z., J.W. Lee, K. Chandran, S. Kim and S.K. Khanal. 2012. Nitrous oxide (N₂ O) emission from aquaculture: a review. *Environmental Science and Technology* 46(12): 6470–6480.

³⁶ Raul, C., Pattanaik, S. S., Prakash, S., Sreedharan, K., & Bharti, S. (2020). Greenhouse gas emissions from aquaculture systems. *World Aquac*, 57, 57-61.

³⁷ Macreadie, P.I., Anton, A., Raven, J.A., Beaumont, N., Connolly, R.M., Friess, D.A., Kelleway, J.J., Kennedy, H., Kuwae, T., Lavery, P.S. and Lovelock, C.E., 2019. The future of Blue Carbon science. *Nature communications*, 10(1), p.3998.

³⁸ Mcleod, Elizabeth, Gail L. Chmura, Steven Bouillon, Rodney Salm, Mats Björk, Carlos M. Duarte, Catherine E. Lovelock, William H. Schlesinger, and Brian R. Silliman. "A blueprint for blue carbon: toward an improved understanding of the role of vegetated coastal habitats in sequestering CO₂." *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment* 9, no. 10 (2011): 552-560.

³⁹ Ahmed, Nesar, Stuart W. Bunting, Marion Glaser, Mark S. Flaherty, and James S. Diana. "Can greening of aquaculture sequester blue carbon?." *Ambio* 46 (2017): 468-477.

can be mitigated against. IMTA improves efficiency and therefore presents a compelling option to reduce GHG emissions. For example, the growth of seaweeds or marine macroalgae has the potential to act as CO₂ sink due to their capacity for photosynthetically driven CO₂ assimilation⁴⁰.

Improved environmental and economic sustainability due to increased efficiency of production in aquaculture has helped reduce the overall carbon footprint⁴¹.

The multi-trophic production of many products in an IMTA system complies with the legal requirements for production under regulation and licencing with regard to the above mentioned environmental criteria. IMTA adds to the ecosystems services of seafood production to a greater extent than monoculture, helping to maintain ecosystems within their natural balance, for this reason IMTA meets the standards for beyond compliance under the various aforementioned certification schemes but is not recognised.

Land-based IMTA as practiced at the IMTA lab South Africa is currently recognized by the WWF SASAI as a sustainable practice due to the recirculation of seawater at the site, resulting in low amounts of waste discharged into the surrounding environment, and farming of low-trophic species. The lab is in fact the only integrated abalone-*Ulva* farm in South Africa that recirculates its seawater by making use of the bioremediation capacity of *Ulva*. The use of IMTA grown *Ulva* (grown in the abalone effluent) results in a 20% reduction in the use of fishmeal based formulated feeds and a significant reduction in pumping costs (an estimated 40% saving in electrical costs). Alongside the use of two wind-turbines at this site, IMTA lab SA is well on its way to meet the standards for beyond compliance under the various certification schemes and is presently seeking accreditation from schemes such as the ASC.

⁴⁰ Chung, Ik Kyo, John Beardall, Smita Mehta, Dinabandhu Sahoo, and Slobodanka Stojkovic. "Using marine macroalgae for carbon sequestration: a critical appraisal." *Journal of applied phycology* 23 (2011): 877-886.

⁴¹ Boyd, Claude E., et al. "Achieving sustainable aquaculture: Historical and current perspectives and future needs and challenges." *Journal of the World Aquaculture Society* 51.3 (2020): 578-633.

Table 1. Standards Beyond Compliance

#	Certification Scheme	Link
1	Organic - IFOAM	IFOAM - Organics International Home
2	EU Organic Regulation	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:02018R0848-20220101&from=EN
3	ASC - The Aquaculture Stewardship Council	https://www.asc-aqua.org/
4	ASC-MSC Seaweed standard	ASC-MSC Seaweed Standard - ASC International (asc-aqua.org)
5	MSC – The Marine Stewardship Council	https://www.msc.org/?gclid=Cj0KCQjw--2aBhD5ARIsALiRlWBRtrhLWwRQLY-snx11jvJfU-F9Oqfwy6DhDbwbFqWxATjrFiPuP0aAga5EALw_wcB
6	GAS – Global Seafood Alliance	https://www.globalseafood.org/
7	BAP – Best Aquaculture Practices	https://www.bapcertification.org/
8	Global GAP – Standards for Good Agricultural Practices	https://www.globalgap.org/uk_en/
9	EU Organic Standard for Seaweed	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:204:0015:0034:EN:PDF
10	Soil Association Organic Seaweed Standards	https://www.soilassociation.org/media/18615/seaweed-standards.pdf
11	ISO Standard ISO/TC 234 Fisheries and Aquaculture	https://www.iso.org/committee/541071.html
12	WWF South African Sustainable Seafood Initiative	https://wwfsassi.co.za/

6 Limitations for IMTA System

6.1 Regulatory constraints and policy

While aquaculture is significantly regulated in Europe, there are substantial differences in legislation at national level. To effectively integrate and promote the adoption of IMTA across various sites and systems, considerable changes to the existing system are necessary.

There is a lack of structure in the licensing process for aquaculture farmers who wish to obtain a permit for IMTA⁴². Issues in regulations, or lack of regulations in relation to IMTA systems hinder the transitioning from monoculture to polyculture⁴³. This is prevalent in IMTA systems incorporating seaweed and other low trophic species, where there are fewer food regulations for lower-level trophic organisms. Furthermore, new technology and production systems often find themselves beyond current certification and compliance schemes such as re-circulating aquaculture systems (RAS).

An objective of the ASTRAL project is the establishment of New Value Chains to support sustainable aquaculture developments. Robust regulatory and legislative procedures are key to achieving this goal. ASTRAL will further develop this recommendation in task 7.7 (Desktop and empirical studies on governance, policy, food-safety/consumer trust and social acceptability).

Current aquaculture regulation originates from monoculture practises as such legislation barriers and issues related to the regulatory system have been identified as some of the most challenging obstacles when setting up an IMTA system⁴⁴. The lack of licencing and dedicated aquaculture policy for IMTA is a limiting factor, alongside the potentially lengthy licencing procedures for the co-cultivation of multiple species.

The EU H2020 project GAIN found that addressing current regulatory barriers to the circular economy applied to aquatic production, through integrated policy formulation is key to the advancement of the industry. The EU regulatory framework guarantees highest standards of food safety and

⁴² Alexander, K.A. and Hughes, A.D. (2017). A problem shared: Technology transfer and development in European integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA). *Aquaculture*, 473, pp.13–19. doi:10.1016/j.aquaculture.2017.01.029.

⁴³ Mildenerger, J., Stangeland, J.K. and Rebours, C. (2022). Antioxidative activities, phenolic compounds and marine food allergens in the macroalgae *Saccharina latissima* produced in integrated multi-trophic aquaculture systems. *Aquaculture*, 546, p.737386. doi:10.1016/j.aquaculture.2021.737386.

⁴⁴ Kleitou et al., 2018. Is Europe ready for integrated multi-trophic aquaculture? A survey on the perspectives of European farmers and scientists with IMTA experience, *Aquaculture*, Volume 490, 136-148, ISSN 0044-8486, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2018.02.035>.

traceability⁴⁵, however, some regulations may pose constraints inhibiting the full implementation of circular economy in the aquaculture sector.

Regulation (EC) No. 767/2009⁴⁶ on the placing on the market and use of feed, prohibits the use of animal waste as a food source for any other animal, both for food producing and non-food producing animals (Article 6, Annex III). This prohibition is a solid barrier to the production of extractive species within IMTA production systems which are co-cultivated with a fed species. Alexandar *et al* 2015⁴⁷ suggest that regulatory reform may be needed in Europe in relation to the transfer of disease, fish health and food safety to allow expansion of IMTA.

The Aquaculture Advisory Council (AAC) encourage the practice of IMTA for its circularity obtained from the removal of nutrients in the water column from neighbouring finfish aquaculture (AAC, 2021).

6.2 Certification

Current certification schemes are focused on monoculture. Criteria for certification of all the ASTRAL species exists under the certification schemes, however the IMTA production systems and the benefits that they bring are not currently addressed in these schemes.

6.3 Markets

There are well-established markets and trade routes for any individual finfish and shellfish species/product generated. Although still in its infancy, the seaweed sector is slowly developing with increasing interest and incentive for developing trade and markets for relevant seaweed species and products. Existing markets operate on a species- or product-specific basis. IMTA being a new production concept, a specific market for IMTA products does not yet exist. Adding an 'IMTA label' to the product could raise consumer awareness and trust in emerging and sustainable food production systems. Furthermore, such labelling could generate economic incentives for producers by offering a premium on IMTA products. However, the consumer must be aware of the benefits of IMTA. ASTRAL will deliver a business model in Task 6.4 towards feasible, profitable, circular aquaculture management and operation.

⁴⁵<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5cb0de844&appId=PPGMS>

⁴⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:229:0001:0028:EN:PDF>

⁴⁷ Alexandar, K.A., et al. The implications of aquaculture policy and regulation for the development of integrated multi-trophic aquaculture in Europe. *Aquaculture*, Volume 443, 2015, 16-23, ISSN 0044-8486, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2015.03.005>.

7 Recommendations

The European Commission's Farm to Fork⁴⁸ strategy aims to develop current aquaculture, to be more sustainable, to produce more affordable products, improve the welfare of both the environment and animals, and create a more circular system biologically and economically. Within the Farm to Fork Strategy and the Biodiversity Strategy, the Commission has defined the objective of 'at least 25% of the EU's agricultural land under organic farming and a significant increase in organic aquaculture by 2030'. As IMTA progresses, it has the potential to conform to organic standards thus adding to the goals of the Farm to Fork strategy and the organic food movement worldwide.

While all the species being produced as part of the ASTRAL IMTA value chains are included in established certification schemes, none of these beyond compliance schemes yet recognise the IMTA approach and the IMTA products they cultivate, for this reason the recommendation is that IMTA produce should align with the current standards while the certification schemes develop their approach to this new integrated way of producing seafood.

Legislation and the resulting administrative processes must be reviewed to facilitate and support the emergence of new IMTA approaches. The partition of regulatory frameworks for each trophic group creates inefficiencies and barriers for businesses to implement IMTA production within a single site.

National policies should be further developed to support the development of IMTA as a viable food production method in the aquaculture sector, this should include governmental incentives to encourage farmers to diversify to this method of farming.

Further research is required into the food safety aspects of IMTA produced food and a review of legislation may be warranted.

⁴⁸ Council conclusions on the Farm to Fork strategy: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/46419/st12099-en20.pdf>.

8 Conclusion

Many jurisdictions have processes, regulations, policies and voluntary codes to guide the aquaculture industry, all of which have a focus on environmental and social acceptance as well as high quality and reliable food production, however, IMTA is not recognised as an established method to meet these parameters, this needs to be reviewed. Certification and the implementation of industry standards dedicated to IMTA are required if this method of food production is to gain traction in the market alongside existing monoculture products.

Dedicated certification for IMTA products is needed to show potential customers that these products have been farmed in sustainable way, making use of the valuable aquaculture resource while creating beneficial ecosystem services increasing circularity and reducing waste.

Further information can be found on the ASTRAL website. <https://www.astral-project.eu/>

Informative videos about the ASTRAL project can be viewed on the ASTRAL YouTube Channel -

[ASTRAL H2020 - YouTube](#)

9 Appendices

APPENDIX 1. KEY POLICY DOCUMENTATION

Jurisdiction (country)	Document name	Link
EU (Ireland)	The National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture	https://assets.gov.ie/99298/a0c7bd0c-212c-43cf-a380-2f4704b93fcc.pdf
	A new Strategic vision for sustainable aquaculture production and consumption in the European Union (Blue farming in the European Green Deal)	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/e8bd0eb1-093a-11ec-b5d3-01aa75ed71a1
	Accelerating 2030 Agenda Integration: Aligning National Development Plans with the Sustainable Development Goals	https://sdgs.un.org/sites/default/files/2022-01/UNU-IAS-PB-No25-2021.pdf
	Farm to Fork Strategy	https://www.bordbia.ie/industry/news/food-alerts/2020/eu-commission-farm-to-fork-strategy/
	Strategic guidelines for a more sustainable and competitive EU aquaculture for the period 2021 to 2030	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2021:236:FIN
	Mid-Term Assessment for the National Strategic Plan for Sustainable Aquaculture Development	https://assets.gov.ie/99297/f7121c52-6589-4612-b11d-8efef8d2ab74.pdf
	National Marine Planning Framework – Project Ireland 2040	https://www.npf.ie/wp-content/uploads/Project-Ireland-2040-NPF.pdf
	The EU's Climate Adaptation Strategy	https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/adaptation-climate-change/eu-adaptation-strategy_en
	DAFM 'Food Wise 2025'	https://www.gov.ie/en/publication/a6b0d-food-wise-2025/
	Food Vision 2030	https://www.gov.ie/en/publication/c73a3-food-vision-2030-a-world-leader-in-sustainable-food-systems/

UK (Scotland)	Seaweed Cultivation Policy Statement 2017 [SCPS]	https://www.gov.scot/publications/seaweed-cultivation-policy-statement-2017/pages/2/
	Scotland's National Marine Plan (Marine Act 2010) [NMP]	https://www.gov.scot/publications/scotlands-national-marine-plan/
	UK Marine Policy Statement 2011 [MPS]	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/uk-marine-policy-statement
	Statement on the Seaweed Review (Scot Gov) ⁴⁹	https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/speech-statement/2022/02/statement-seaweed-review/documents/statement-seaweed-review/statement-seaweed-review/govscot%3Adocument/statement-seaweed-review.pdf
	OSPAR 2014-02 'OSPAR Joint Assessment and Monitoring Programme (JAMP) 2014-2021' Update 2018' (Table II).	https://marine.gov.scot/sma/assessment/seaweed-harvesting-and-cultivation
	United Nations Sustainable Development Goals	https://sdgs.un.org/goals
	Our Seas - A shared resource. High level marine objectives. HM Government 2009	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/our-seas-a-shared-resource-high-level-marine-objectives
Africa (South Africa)	Marine Aquaculture Policy Implementation Plan 2009 – 2014	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1jMDk4Yk6MIGLgVYAHu99A9noQQsdUfX2/view?usp=share_link
	Aquaculture Research and Technology Development Programme for South Africa 2012	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1tJuvoANHh8XNuLaH9-R3kWjnAAJw9nm5/view?usp=share_link
	National Aquaculture Strategic Framework 2012	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1IJ2D_pgvFvQWVy6A4TYs6qmDhKkcNI4P/view?usp=share_link
	National Aquaculture Strategic Framework 2013	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1mDhGEM9rjJ8kaYk-2HtWERN_YmMw1ghy/view?usp=share_link

⁴⁹ An effective ban on mechanical wild harvesting through amendment to the Scottish Crown Estate Act 2019, which prohibits the wild harvest of certain kelp species inhibiting the growth or recovery of the plant.

	Operation Phakisa 'Unlocking the Oceans Economy' Initiative 2014	https://www.operationphakisa.gov.za/operations/oel/pages/default.aspx
	National Strategic Framework for Aquatic Animal Health	https://drive.google.com/file/d/13iCASmSOFWGsi2vvpPoDMS163PVDOYJz/view?usp=share_link
South America (Brazil)	National plan for Aquaculture Development – PNDA – 2022-2032	https://www.gov.br/agricultura/pt-br/assuntos/mpa/aquicultura-1/plano-nacional-de-desenvolvimento-da-aquicultura-pnda-2022-2032
South America (Argentina)	Productive Argentina Plan 2030. Aquaculture in Argentina: network of actors, production processes and spaces for adding value. In search of the export boost for aquaculture products.	https://www.argentina.gob.ar/produccion/argentina-productiva-2030 https://www.argentina.gob.ar/sites/default/files/2021/03/dt_13_-_acuicultura.pdf
	Analysis of the Argentine aquaculture sector 2022.	https://www.magyp.gob.ar/sitio/areas/acuicultura/Informes/_archivos/000001_Analisis%20del%20Sector%20Acu%C3%ADcola%20Argentino.pdf
	Analysis of large-scale intensive salmonid aquaculture in the Beagle Channel as a strategy for the development of Tierra del Fuego.	http://www.scielo.org.ar/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S2525-12952020000100006
	Innovacua Program: Sustainable Aquaculture in a multitrophic marine farm.	http://www.agencia.mincyt.gob.ar/upload/Bases%20y%20Condiciones%20INNOVACUA%202016_final.pdf

APPENDIX 2. NATIONAL LEGISLATION

Jurisdiction (country)	Document name	Link
EU (Ireland)	Marine Spatial Framework Directive (Directive 2014/89/EU)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2014.257.01.0135.01.ENG%20
	Water Framework Directive (Directive 2000/60/EC)	https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/water/water-framework-directive_en
	Shellfish Waters Directive (Directive 2006/113/EC)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2006:376:0014:0020:EN:PDF
	The Habitats Directive (Directive 92/43/EEC)	https://www.npws.ie/legislation/eu-directives
	The Birds Directive (Directive 2009/147/EC)	
	Natura 2000	https://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/natura2000/index_en.htm
	Listed Diseases Directive (Directive 2006/88/EC)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2006:328:0014:0056:en:PDF
	Health of Aquaculture Animals and Products Regulations 2008 (Directive No. 2006/88/EC)	
	Marine Strategy Framework Directive (Directive 2008/56/EC)	https://www.eea.europa.eu/policy-documents/2008-56-ec
	Hazardous Waste Directive (Directive 2000/532/EC)	https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/eur38210.pdf
	Waste Directive (Directive 2006/12/EC)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2006:114:0009:0021:en:PDF
	Environmental Liability Directive (Directive 2004/35/EC)	https://www.eumonitor.eu/9353000/1/j4nvk6yhcbpeywk_j9vvik7m1c3gyxp/vitgbgifu8xw
	Aarhus Convention (2003/4/EC, 2003/35/EC)	https://environment.ec.europa.eu/law-and-governance/aarhus_en
	Environmental Impact Assessment Directive (Directive 2014/52/EU)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014L0052&rid=1

	Dangerous Substances Directive (Directive 2006/11/EC)	https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/eur62328.pdf
	Animal Health Law (Regulation 2016/429/EU)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016R0429
	Use of Alien & Locally Absent Species in Aquaculture (Regulation 708/2007/EC)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2007:168:0001:0017:EN:PDF
	Residues of Veterinary Medicinal Products (Directive 96/23/EC)	https://food.ec.europa.eu/safety/chemical-safety/residues-veterinary-medicinal-products_en
	Hygiene Rules for Food of Animal Origin (Regulation 853/2004/EC)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32004R0853
	Directive (EU) 2019/904 on reducing the impact of certain plastic products on the environment	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/904/oj
UK (Scotland)	Wildlife and Natural Environment (Scotland) Act 2011	https://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2011/6/contents/enacted
	Crown Estate Act 2019	https://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2019/1/contents/enacted
	Marine (Scotland) Act 2010	https://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2010/5/contents
	The Waste (Scotland) Regulations 2012	https://www.legislation.gov.uk/sdsi/2012/9780111016657/content_s
	Marine and Coastal Access Act 2009 [MCAA]	https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2009/23/contents
	The Food and Environment Protection Act 1985	https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1985/48
Africa (South Africa)	Guide to Authorization Requirements for Aquaculture in South Africa, 2022	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1WIDGCQ_eKiQiJV0IYIgtQ7Szx8VmXgX7/view?usp=share_link
	The Marine Living Resources Act, 1998 (Act No. 18 of 1998)	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ARRjGmaxaiv2CIIJ4kWRygtQ8fgsM6OO/view?usp=share_link
	The National Environmental Management: Integrated Coastal Management Amendment Act, 2014 (Act No. 36 of 2014) (GN 38171)	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1gY428gWhDtVuWgd_Xw7yyx3Tugt5qpyo/view?usp=share_link
	The National Environmental Management Act, 1998 (Act No. 107 of 1998): Environmental Impact Assessment Regulations, 2014 (GN 38282)	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ZFW3S0QGIUKIdFQHeCRFXAViEcrfVe7V/view?usp=share_link

The National Environmental Management Act, 1998 (Act No. 107 of 1998) (NEMA)	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1kg06lgsM-O1NDjpomVsgGU6ndOMEpclu/view?usp=share_link
The National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act, 2004 (Act No. 10 of 2004) (NEM: BA)	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1a2NljigG_1txOQbBMvV_dc0dWMPvJ4TA/view?usp=share_link
The National Environmental Management: Protected Areas Act, 2003 (Act No. 10 of 2003)	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Sn_cpmBvozyHya2REyk8wZLxJkahXTAD/view?usp=share_link
The National Environmental Management: Waste Act, 2008 (Act No. 59 of 2008)	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1kkDibROnJNGnszcbdGyQ_qutkj-B8pJg/view?usp=share_link
The National Environmental Management: Air Quality Act, 2004 (Act No. 39 of 2004)	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1y3ugm6bzBbCmVQfTiEk4fdp4sMpaI8AX/view?usp=share_link
The National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act, 2004 (Act No. 10 of 2004): Alien and Invasive Species Regulations, 2020 (GN 43726)	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1272TJHJt7ZdJVclkc0oNRfVxC3NMTJ3c/view?usp=share_link
The National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act, 2004 (Act No. 10 of 2004): Threatened and Protected Marine Species Regulations, 2017	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1DI3a0xY_2YxvipRSaLLJ3aDuFlcBw0Xs/view?usp=share_link
The Animal Diseases Act, 1984 (Act 35 of 1984)	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1QIsMmNTUE4XQNNr7r3DbWgn2h6fPbe4C/view?usp=share_link
The Animal Protection Act, 1962 (Act No. 71 of 1962)	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1CoD_Os5mfxpRJu-eA2DcRIOLTr7e6ddF/view?usp=share_link
The Seashore Act, 1935 (Act No. 21 of 1935)	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1EJXUzlQaqrTM7fpuHDJ8lmlPvZ0sl7Wu/view?usp=share_link
The Sea Birds and Seals Protection Act, 1973 (Act No. 46 of 1973)	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ySjQXBoah-YMH_D3m_MhOpPE3Wvj88Rj/view?usp=share_link
The Fertilizers, Farm Feeds, Agricultural Remedies and Stock Remedies Act, 1947 (Act No. 36 of 1947)	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1oETz-JgybSXhQUJPLdxcDNhtjaNfKW4l/view?usp=share_link
The Medicines and Related Substances Act, 1965 (Act No. 101 of 1965)	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ofVGJKkvVd6IV-i8Bv-NoJlmWaLmpBH1/view?usp=share_link

	The National Health Act, 2003 (Act No. 61 of 2003);	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1fgEJDLBAfW_AOu5-dRVGuz9d5irNJldn/view?usp=share_link
	The Foodstuffs, Cosmetics and Disinfectants Act, 1972 (Act No. 54 of 1972)	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1aBa_7ikB0LyeNZwm8nqxzCYQgPvUCoCl/view?usp=share_link
	The National Regulator for Compulsory Specifications Act, 2008 (Act No. 5 of 2008)	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1sauNrumleOHvjzOtdFM6T2hbdAnj19yA/view?usp=share_link
South America (Brazil)	National Legislation for Aquaculture - Law Number 767955 /2017	http://www.camara.gov.br/sileg/integras/767955.pdf
	Resolution CONAMA Number 312 /2002 Use of coastal area	http://conama.mma.gov.br/index.php?option=com_sisconama&view=reuniao&id=2128
	Resolution CONAMA Number 357 /2005 Water quality classification rectification 393 /2007; 397 /2008; 410 /2009 and 430 /2011	https://www.icmbio.gov.br/cepsul/images/stories/legislacao/Resolucao/2005/res_conama_357_2005_classificacao_corpos_agua_rtfcd_altrd_res_393_2007_397_2008_410_2009_430_2011.pdf
	Resolution CONAMA Number 459 /2013 Rules for aquaculture implementation II	https://www.icmbio.gov.br/cepsul/images/stories/legislacao/Resolucao/2013/res_conama_459_2013_alt_res_conama_413_2009_que_trata_licenciamento_ambiental_aquicultura.pdf
	Resolution CONAMA Number 413 /2009 Rules for aquaculture implementation I	https://www.icmbio.gov.br/cepsul/images/stories/legislacao/Resolucao/2009/RES_CONAMA_N413_2009.pdf
South America (Argentina)	Law 18.284/69. Argentine Food Code.	https://www.argentina.gob.ar/normativa/nacional/ley-18284-21841
	Decree 2.126/71. Regulates the Argentine Food Code.	https://www.argentina.gob.ar/normativa/nacional/decreto-2126-1971-209207
	Argentine Food Code - Chapter VI (Updated 2022). Meat and Related Foods. Denomination of Fishing and Aquaculture Products.	https://alimentosargentinos.magyp.gob.ar/contenido/marco/CAA/Capitulo_06.htm
	Law 24.375/94. Law approving the Convention on Biological Diversity. Objectives: the conservation of biological diversity, the sustainable use	https://www.argentina.gob.ar/normativa/nacional/ley-25675-79980/texto

of its components and the fair and equitable sharing of the benefits derived from the use of genetic resources

Law 25.675/02. General Environmental Law.

<http://servicios.infoleg.gob.ar/infolegInternet/anexos/100000-104999/102388/norma.htm>

Resolution 1.314/04. Regulates the production of Live Aquatic Organisms in aquaculture ventures.

<https://www.argentina.gob.ar/normativa/nacional/ley-25675-79980/texto>

Resolution 829/06. General provisions and definitions on bivalve molluscs intended for human consumption

<https://www.argentina.gob.ar/normativa/nacional/resoluci%C3%B3n-829-2006-122869/texto>

Resolution 433/10. Recognizes aquaculture production areas in the province of Tierra del Fuego according to Resolution 966/07.

<https://www.argentina.gob.ar/normativa/nacional/resoluci%C3%B3n-433-2010-169167/texto>

Law 27,231/15. Sustainable Development of the Aquaculture Sector. Complemented and modified by 2,3,4 and 5.

<https://www.argentina.gob.ar/normativa/nacional/ley-27231-257444/texto>

Decree 692/17. Regulation of Law 27,231/15.

<https://www.argentina.gob.ar/normativa/nacional/decreto-692-2017-278895/texto>

Deposition 66/21. Approves the Operational Manual of the Promotion and Development Regime for the growth of the Aquaculture Sector. See Manual 2021_Resolution_66_Annex.pdf.

<https://www.argentina.gob.ar/normativa/nacional/disposici%C3%B3n-66-2021-353475/texto>

Deposition 67/21. Approves the Procedure Manual for Requests for Contribution of the Promotion and Development Regime for the growth of the Aquaculture Sector. See Manual 2021_Resolution_67_Annex.pdf.

<https://www.argentina.gob.ar/normativa/nacional/disposici%C3%B3n-67-2021-350942/texto>

Deposition 22/22. Regulations for requests for contributions to the National Fund for the Development of Aquaculture Activities.

<https://www.argentina.gob.ar/normativa/nacional/disposici%C3%B3n-22-2022-376514/texto>

Law 55/92. Environment Law.

<https://www.argentina.gob.ar/normativa/provincial/ley-55-123456789-0abc-defg-945-0000vvorpyel/actualizacion>

Decree 1333/93. Regulatory of Law 55/1992. Annex II: Water and its contamination. Annex III: Soils. Annex VII: Environmental impact. Environmental Impact Assessment. Definition. EIA requirements. Project Notice Guide.

<https://www.argentina.gob.ar/ciencia/agencia/normativa-ambiental-tierra-del-fuego-antartida-islas>

Law 244/95. Fishing Law. Chapter IX Aquaculture.	http://www.legistdf.gob.ar/lp/leyes/Provinciales/LEYP244.pdf
Law 537/01. Replaces article 32 of Chapter IX of Provincial Law No. 244 on duration and area of aquaculture concessions.	https://argentambiental.com/legislacion/tierra-del-fuego/ley-537-pesca/
Law 1126/16. Comprehensive Water Resources Management Framework.	http://www.legistdf.gob.ar/lp/leyes/Provinciales/LEYP1126.pdf
Law 1168/17. Adherence to the National Aquaculture Law.	http://www.legistdf.gob.ar/lp/leyes/Provinciales/LEYP1168.pdf
Law 1335/21. Prohibition of cultivation and production of salmonids.	http://www.legistdf.gob.ar/lp/leyes/Provinciales/LEYP1355.pdf

APPENDIX 3. LINKS TO REGULATORY PERMIT & LICENCING

Jurisdiction (country)	Document name	Link
EU (Ireland)	Fisheries (Amendment) Act 1997, No. 23	https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/1997/act/23/enacted/en/html
	Fisheries and Foreshore (Amendment) Act 1998, No. 54 [Sections 2,3 and 4]	https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/1998/act/54/enacted/en/html
	Fisheries (Amendment) Act 2001, No. 40	https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2001/act/40/enacted/en/html
	Sea-Fisheries and Maritime Jurisdiction Act 2006, No. 8 [Section 101]	https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2006/act/8/enacted/en/html
	Aquaculture (Licence Application) Regulations, 1998 S.I. NO. 236 OF 1998, as amended by S.I. No. 145 of 2001 and S.I. No. 197 of 2006 and S.I. No 301 of 2012 and S.I. No 410 of 2012	https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2018/si/240/made/en/print
	Strategy for improved pest control on Irish salmon farms 2008	https://assets.gov.ie/99272/33314a8b-df65-4807-9d65-27527426e521.pdf
	Aquaculture licence applications may be subject to environmental assessments under the Natural Habitats Regulations if located within or close to Natura 2000 conservation sites.	https://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/natura2000/index_en.htm
	All applications in 'Natura 2000' areas are required to be appropriately assessed for the purpose of environmental compliance with the EU Habitats Directive of 92/43/EEC & Birds Directives 79/409 EEC	https://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/legislation/habitatsdirective/index_en.htm
	The Minister may require an applicant to submit an Environmental Impact Statement if the Minister considers that the proposed aquaculture is likely to have significant effects on the environment Environmental Impact Assessment Directives consolidated in Directive 2011/92/EU.	https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2020/si/191/made/en/print
Seafood is also subject to various food safety legislation which governs stock traceability (Regulation 178/2002/EC).	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:02002R0178-20140630&rid=1	

	Monitoring Protocol No. 3 for Offshore Finfish Farms - Sea Lice Monitoring and Control 2000	https://assets.gov.ie/99273/b716130e-5144-466e-a23f-d90af3d9f6d8.pdf
	ISO/TC 234 Fisheries and aquaculture	https://www.iso.org/committee/541071.html
	Movement of fish, shellfish and invertebrates listed under: Fish Health Approval is a requirement under Article 176 of the EU Animal Health Regulation 2016/429.	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32016R0429&qid=1642437288727
	EPR compliance schemes for reduction of plastics in the marine environment Directive (EU) 2019/904 on reducing the impact of certain plastic products on the environment	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=LEGISSUM:4393034
UK (Scotland)	Seaweed farm licence from Marine Scotland (see Marine Act 2010)	https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/adv-ice-and-guidance/2020/02/marine-licensing-applications-and-guidance/documents/applications/algal-farms-application/algal-farms-application/govscot%3Adocument/Algal%2Bfarms%2Bapplication.pdf
	Crown Estate lease from Crown Estate Scotland (see Crown Estate Bill)	https://www.crownestatescotland.com/scotlands-property/marine/aquaculture
	Shellfish license from Local Planning Authority (e.g. Argyll and Bute)	Aquaculture (argyll-bute.gov.uk)
	Shellfish compliance measures managed by the Fish Health Inspectorate (FHI) Scotland (e.g. management of shellfish movements and Biosecurity)	https://www.gov.scot/policies/fish-health-inspectorate/
	Plastic Management Plan	https://www.legislation.gov.uk/sdsi/2012/9780111016657/contents
	Biosecurity Plan (Wildlife and Natural Environment (Scotland) Act 2011)	
	The Food Safety (Fishery Products and Live Shellfish) (Hygiene) Regulations 1998	https://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/1998/994/regulation/8/made
Africa (South Africa)	Integrated marine aquaculture grow out permit: (Farming, Transport, Fish Processing Establishment, and Broodstock Collection)	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1V8xWSFtQnKQ54KHM0MRIdY3wq65hcgoc/view?usp=share_link
	Integrated marine aquaculture hatchery permit: (Hatchery, Broodstock Collection, and Transport)	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1V8xWSFtQnKQ54KHM0MRIdY3wq65hcgoc/view?usp=share_link
	Permit to transport marine aquaculture fish and fish product(s)	https://drive.google.com/file/d/134Ei7ulmWz3s0ov0fnAEFxaMtcMD-DgR/view?usp=share_link

	Permit to operate a marine aquaculture Fish Processing Establishment (FPE)	https://drive.google.com/file/d/134Ei7ulmWz3s0ov0fnAEFxaMtcMD-DgR/view?usp=share_link
	Permit for the purposes of diving and possession of prohibited gear in the listed areas	https://drive.google.com/file/d/134Ei7ulmWz3s0ov0fnAEFxaMtcMD-DgR/view?usp=share_link
	Permit for marine aquaculture scientific investigations and practical experiments	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1k6mc97MKB3kFhUEPAtxvdvW2Lg9IlpA-/view?usp=share_link
	Permit to import marine aquaculture fish and fish product(s)	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1UkXrubHBt85geuLsSUX9JQ_cQF9jYHKq/view?usp=share_link
	Permit to export marine aquaculture fish and fish product(s)	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1OYGdam8YeQA7H_3ywpOtdvQzrDeor9MC/view?usp=share_link
	9) Health Management Procedures for South African Abalone Produced for Export	
South America (Brazil)	Resolution CONSEMA number 462/2022	https://www.sema.rs.gov.br/upload/arquivos/202207/13113810-462-2022-aquicultura.pdf
South America (Argentina)	Ordinance 3-02 (DNS). Standards for the construction of ships and naval artifacts, including pontoons.	https://www.ecofield.net/Legales/PNA/Tomo1-regimen_tecn_buque/023.pdf
	Ordinance 5-14 (DNS). Rules for floating constructions not intended for navigation, including cages.	https://www.argentina.gob.ar/normativa/nacional/disposici%C3%B3n-3-2009-153379/texto
	Resolution 51/01. Aquatic Animal Diseases Program	http://www.senasa.gob.ar/normativas/resolucion-51-2001-senasa-servicio-nacional-de-sanidad-y-calidad-agroalimentaria
	Resolution 433/10. Recognize bivalve mollusc production areas ARTF in TDF.	https://www.argentina.gob.ar/normativa/nacional/resoluci%C3%B3n-433-2010-169167
	Resolution 387/13. Aquaculture Technicians Registry. See annexes	http://www.senasa.gob.ar/resolucion-3872013
	Law 597/03. Tax Land: "Zoning, conditions and restrictions of use of the geographical area called "Southwestern sector of the Argentine territory of the Big Island of Tierra del Fuego".	http://www.legistdf.gob.ar/lp/leyes/Provinciales/LEYP597.pdf

Resolution 966/07. Establishes zones in the process of classification for the production of bivalve molluscs. Modified by Resolution 04/14.	https://www.magyp.gob.ar/sitio/areas/acuicultura/zonificacion/_archivos//120424_Informes%20por%20Provincias/120925_Provincia%20de%20Tierra%20del%20Fuego.pdf
Resolution 04/14. Modifies Resolution 966/07. Modification of areas for the production of bivalves for human consumption.	http://www.senasa.gob.ar/normativas/disposicion-4-2014-senasa-servicio-nacional-de-sanidad-y-calidad-agroalimentaria
Resolution 11/22. Labelling of aquaculture products.	https://www.argentina.gob.ar/normativa/nacional/resoluci%C3%B3n-11-2022-375894/texto

APPENDIX 4: PERMITS/LICENCES & COMPLIANCE

Jurisdiction (country)	Permits & Licences	Compliance
EU (Ireland)	Aquaculture Licence	Benthic Monitoring Protocol
		Water Monitoring Protocol
		Sealice Monitoring Protocol
		Annual DAFM Vet Inspection
		Annual DAFM Engineering Inspection
	Foreshore Licence	
	Discharge Licence	Discharge Licence Monitoring
Sale of product	The National Surveillance Monitoring Programme for residues in farmed fish	
	Food safety authority of Ireland	
UK (Scotland)	Seaweed farm licence from Marine Scotland (see Marine Act 2010)	https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/advice-and-guidance/2020/02/marine-licensing-applications-and-guidance/documents/applications/algal-farms-application/algal-farms-application/govscot%3Adocument/Algal%2Bfarms%2Bapplication.pdf
	Crown Estate lease from Crown Estate Scotland (see Crown Estate Bill)	https://www.crownestatescotland.com/scotlands-property/marine/aquaculture
	Shellfish license from Local Planning Authority (e.g. Argyll and Bute)	Aquaculture (argyll-bute.gov.uk)
Africa (South Africa)	Integrated marine aquaculture grow out permit: (Farming, Transport, Fish Processing Establishment, and Broodstock Collection)	

	Integrated marine aquaculture hatchery permit: (Hatchery, Broodstock Collection, and Transport)	
	Permit to transport marine aquaculture fish and fish product(s)	
	Permit to operate a marine aquaculture Fish Processing Establishment (FPE)	
	Permit for the purposes of diving and possession of prohibited gear in the listed areas	
	Permit to export marine aquaculture fish and fish product(s)	
	Permit for the purposes of diving and possession of prohibited gear in the listed areas	
South America (Brazil)		Regular Site Inspection
	Aquaculture licence	Regular Biosecurity inspection
		Phytoplankton monitoring – Toxin analysis
	Discharge licence	Discharge monitoring and water quality report
South America (Argentina)	Procedures and control for Bivalve Molluscs.	Continuous control of the entire production chain
	Aquaculture zone maintenance audit and supervision manuals.	Regular Site Inspection
	Classification of mollusk production areas	Regular monitoring – Toxin and chemical analysis